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ORCHESTRA

**Open Architecture and Spatial Data Infrastructure for
Risk Management**

Integrated Project

Priority 2.3.2.9 Improving Risk Management

WP3.6 – OA Service Implementation

**Implementation Specification of the User Manage-
ment Service**

Revision [1.0 / 1.3]

Document Control Page

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Table of Contents

i.	Preface.....	8
ii.	Relations to the platform-neutral OA Service Specification.....	8
iii.	Future work.....	8
1	Scope.....	9
2	Conventions.....	10
2.1	UML Notation.....	10
2.2	Conformance.....	10
2.2.1	Conformance to the Platform and the OA.....	10
2.2.2	Conformance to the abstract specification of the User Management Service.....	10
2.3	Used parts of other documents.....	10
3	Mapping from an Abstract Specification.....	11
3.1	Service Capabilities Interface.....	11
3.1.1	getCapabilities Operation.....	11
3.1.1.1	OA_GetCapabilitiesRequest Parameter Type.....	11
3.1.1.2	OA_GetCapabilitiesResponse Parameter Type.....	12
3.1.1.3	OA_MI_Service_SpecificCapabilities Parameter Type.....	12
3.2	User Management Service Interface.....	13
3.2.1	createSubject Operation.....	13
3.2.2	deleteSubject Operation.....	14
3.2.3	updateSubject Operation.....	14
3.2.4	createGroup Operation.....	14
3.2.5	deleteGroup Operation.....	14
3.2.6	updateGroup Operation.....	15
3.2.7	addPrincipalToGroup Operation.....	15
3.2.8	removePrincipalFromGroup Operation.....	15
3.2.9	getSubjects Operation.....	15
3.2.10	getGroups Operation.....	16
3.2.11	addPrincipalToSubject Operation.....	16
3.2.12	removePrincipalFromSubject Operation.....	16
4	Platform-specific specification.....	17
4.1	User Management Service Overview.....	17

4.2	Specification of a Profile of Parameter Types used by the Authentication Service	17
4.3	Specification of the getCapabilities Operation.....	19
4.4	Specification of the createSubject Operation	21
4.5	Specification of the deleteSubject Operation	23
4.6	Specification of the updateSubject Operation	25
4.7	Specification of the createGroup Operation	27
4.8	Specification of the deleteGroup Operation	29
4.9	Specification of the updateGroup Operation	31
4.10	Specification of the addPrincipalToGroup Operation	33
4.11	Specification of the removePrincipalFromGroup Operation	35
4.12	Specification of the getSubjects Operation.....	37
4.13	Specification of the getGroups Operation.....	39
4.14	Specification of the addPrincipalToSubject Operation	41
4.15	Specification of the removePrincipalFromSubject Operation	43
5	Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents	45
5.1	XML Schema Documents.....	45
5.1.1	usermanagement_exceptions.xsd	45
5.1.2	usermanagement_types.xsd	47
5.1.3	usermanagement_requests.xsd.....	52
5.2	WSDL Document.....	55
6	Appendix B: UML Model	75
6.1	Static model.....	75
6.2	Dynamic model.....	76

Tables

Table 1: Mapping of operations of the Service Capabilities interface.....	11
Table 2: Mapping of parameters used by the getCapabilities operation	11
Table 3: Mapping of attributes used in getCapabilities request parameter	12
Table 4: Mapping of attributes used in getCapabilities return parameter	12
Table 5: Mapping of attributes used in parameter OA_MI_Service_SpecificCapabilities	12
Table 6: Mapping of operations of the User Management Service interface	13
Table 7: Mapping of parameters used by the createSubject operation	13
Table 8: Mapping of parameters used by the deleteSubject operation	14
Table 9: Mapping of parameters used by the updateSubject operation	14
Table 10: Mapping of parameters used by the createGroup operation	14
Table 11: Mapping of parameters used by the deleteGroup operation	14
Table 12: Mapping of parameters used by the updateGroup operation	15
Table 13: Mapping of parameters used by the addPrincipalToGroup operation	15
Table 14: Mapping of parameters used by the removePrincipalFromGroup operation.....	15
Table 15: Mapping of parameters used by the getSubjects operation	16
Table 16: Mapping of parameters used by the getGroups operation	16
Table 17: Mapping of parameters used by the addPrincipalToSubject operation.....	16
Table 18: Mapping of parameters used by the removePrincipalFromSubject operation.....	16
Table 19: Summary of Service Operations.....	17
Table 20: XML Types.....	18
Table 21: Specification of the getCapabilities Operation	20
Table 22: Specification of the createSubject Operation	21
Table 23: Specification of the deleteSubject Operation.....	24
Table 24: Specification of the updateSubject Operation	25
Table 25: Specification of the createGroup Operation.....	28
Table 26: Specification of the deleteGroup Operation.....	29
Table 27: Specification of the updatGroup Operation.....	31
Table 28: Specification of the addPrincipalToGroup Operation	33
Table 29: Specification of the removePrincipalFromGroup Operation	36
Table 30: Specification of the getSubjects Operation.....	37
Table 31: Specification of the getGroups Operation.....	39
Table 32: Specification of the addPrincipalToSubject Operation	42
Table 33: Specification of the removePrincipalFromSubject Operation	44

i. Preface

The User Management Service is based on the abstract specification of the User Management Service, Version 1.8.

This implementation specification describes the implementation of the User Management Service with respect to the requirements of pilot implementations.

For a detailed description of the authentication service interface please refer to the correspondent abstract specification.

ii. Relations to the platform-neutral OA Service Specification

Derivations from the abstract service specification

The implementation specification of the User Management Services does not require derivations from the abstract specification to accommodate the technical contents of this document.

Modifications of the abstract service specification

Modifications of the abstract specification of the User Management Service are not necessary.

iii. Future work

Improvements in this document are desirable to supported additional subject types (currently only ordinary subjects and groups are supported) as well as the correspondent subject attributes. Future versions might be extended to additionally support the OA_ServiceSubject and OA_ServiceChainSubject types as defined in the abstract specification. Support of additionally subject attributes, providing more complex data structures, is also conceivable.

Implementation Specification of the User Management Service

1 Scope

This document defines an implementation specification of the User Management Service for the ORCHESTRA Web Services Platform 1.1.1 and is based on the Template for the Implementation Specification of ORCHESTRA Services version 1.3. It specifies the interfaces implemented by the discussed service as well as their main purpose in relation to a concrete OSN. It provides a formal description of the implemented operations according to the rules defined in the specification of the ORCHESTRA Web Services Platform.

The current implementation is very basic and only provides key-value pairs, based on LDAP profile, as subject attributes. A MySQL data base is used as persistent storage backend for storage of required information as subjects attributes.

Other structures of subject attributes (resp. other storage devices) may be supported by further versions of this service by implementing correspondent handlers, but this is not subject of this document.

2 Conventions

2.1 UML Notation

All software engineering diagrams in this specification are presented using the Unified Modelling Language (UML) version 2.0 as the conceptual schema language.

2.2 Conformance

2.2.1 Conformance to the Platform and the OA

This implementation specification is conformant to the ORCHESTRA Meta-Model for Services (OMM-Service) and the specification of the ORCHESTRA Web Services Platform.

The data model defined in this document is compliant to the ORCHESTRA Meta-Model for Information (OMM-Info) and its platform specific representation.

The platform specific representation of the data model in XML Schema defined according to the rules of the ORCHESTRA Web Services Platform is ISO/DIS 19136 Geographic information - Geography Markup Language (GML) Version 2.1.2.

The following exception that is in compliance with platform rules apply:

1. Non-geographic Features (“normal classes”) are not derived from GML base types

The Web service specifications presented in this document are compliant to WSDL Version 1.1 with SOAP Version 1.1 HTTP binding.

The possible bindings are:

1. SOAP Version 1.1 HTTP binding

The binding is specified in chapter Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

The message style that shall be used is document/literal non-wrapped. This has the consequence that each operation takes only one single input parameter (an XML element). This XML element is referenced in the wsdl:message which has only one wsdl:part.

The mapping of an operation with multiple parameters to an operation with one single request parameter is subject to the chapter Mapping from an Abstract Specification.

2.2.2 Conformance to the abstract specification of the User Management Service

According to the conformance clause of the abstract specification of the User Management Service, this implementation specification can be considered conformant to the abstract specification.

The derivations from the abstract specification and from the mapping rules are documented in chapter Mapping from an Abstract Specification.

2.3 Used parts of other documents

This document does not use significant parts of other documents.

3 Mapping from an Abstract Specification

The following subchapters defines the mapping between the abstract specification of the Authentication Service and the platform specification for the “ORCHESTRA Web Services Platform”.

3.1 Service Capabilities Interface

The following table lists the mapping between operations of the Service Capabilities Interface:

Abstract Specification	Implementation Specification	Note
getCapabilities	getCapabilities	

Table 1: Mapping of operations of the Service Capabilities interface

The implementation specification of the Service Capabilities Interface is a 1:1 mapping from the abstract interface specification and is syntactically and semantically equivalent, except for service specific capabilities, to the specification of the Service Capabilities Interface.

The implementation specification of the Service Capabilities Interface does not follow strictly the mapping rules of the Platform Specification.

All operations of this interface have exactly 0 or 1 input parameter. A mapping of multiple operation parameters to one single request parameter as required by the document/literal message style is therefore not required.

3.1.1 getCapabilities Operation

This subchapter defines the mapping of the getCapabilities operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
request	OA_GetCapabilitiesRequest	O	request	OA_GetCapabilitiesRequest	M	(1)
return	OA_GetCapabilitiesResponse	M	return	OA_GetCapabilitiesResponse	M	(2)

Table 2: Mapping of parameters used by the getCapabilities operation

(1) The request parameter shall be mandatory in the implementation of the getCapabilities operation.

(2) Note that the type OA_CapabilitiesDocument of the abstract specification has been renamed to OA_GetCapabilitiesResponse for clarity.

3.1.1.1 OA_GetCapabilitiesRequest Parameter Type

This subchapter defines the mapping of the request parameter of the getCapabilities operation.

Attribute of Abstract Spec.			Parameter of Implementation Spec.			Note
acceptFormats	OA_MimeType[0..*]	O	acceptFormats	OA_MimeType[0..*]	O	(1)

acceptSpec Versions	CharacterString[0..*]	O	acceptSpec Versions	CharacterString[0..*]	O
sections	OA_CapabilitiesSections	O	sections	OA_Capabilities Sections	O

Table 3: Mapping of attributes used in getCapabilities request parameter

- (1) Independent of the contents of the acceptFormats attribute, the returned capabilities can always be formatted according to the default MIME type which is defined as “text/xml”.

3.1.1.2 OA_GetCapabilitiesResponse Parameter Type

This subchapter defines the mapping of the return parameter of the getCapabilities operation.

Attribute of Abstract Spec.			Parameter of Implementation Spec.			Note
capability Sections	Binary	M	capability Sections	xsd:anyType	M	(1)
format	OA_MimeType	M	format	OA_MimeType	M	(2)
schemaName	OA_CapabilitiesSchema	M	schemaName	OA_Capabilities Schema	M	
version	CharacterString	M	version	xsd:string	M	

Table 4: Mapping of attributes used in getCapabilities return parameter

- (1) The XML Schema type anyType is used in the implementation specification to allow the capabilities to be structured according to a certain XML Schema which is not predefined here. The capabilities shall be structured according to the schema indicated by the value of the schemaName attribute.
- (2) The value of the format attribute may always denote the default MIME Type “text/xml” indicating that the capabilities are formatted in XML.

3.1.1.3 OA_MI_Service_SpecificCapabilities Parameter Type

Since OA_CapabilitiesDocument contains common service capabilities (OA_MI_ServiceCommonCapabilities) and service specific capabilities (OA_MI_ServiceSpecificCapabilities) this subchapter defines the mapping of the OA_MI_ServiceSpecificCapabilities.

Attribute of Abstract Spec.			Parameter of Implementation Spec.			Note
dynamicAttributesSupported	Boolean	M	dynamicAttributesSupported	xsd:boolean	M	
supportedSubjectAttributeTypes	Sequence_OfType	M	supportedSubjectAttributeTypes	xsd:enumeration	M	

Table 5: Mapping of attributes used in parameter OA_MI_Service_SpecificCapabilities

3.2 User Management Service Interface

The following table lists the mapping between operations of the User Management Service Interface:

Abstract Specification	Implementation Specification	Note
createSubject	createSubject	
deleteSubject	deleteSubject	
updateSubject	updateSubject	
createGroup	createGroup	
deleteGroup	deleteGroup	
updateGroup	updateGroup	
addPrincipalToSubject	addPrincipalToSubject	
removePrincipalFromSubject	removePrincipalFromSubject	
getSubjects	getSubjects	
getGroups	getGroups	
removePrincipalFromGroup	removePrincipalFromGroup	
addPrincipalToGroup	addPrincipalToGroup	

Table 6: Mapping of operations of the User Management Service interface

The implementation specification of the Authentication Interface is a 1:1 mapping from the abstract interface specification and is syntactically and semantically equivalent to the specification of the Authentication Interface.

3.2.1 createSubject Operation

This subchapter defines the mapping of the createSubject operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
subject	OA_Subject	M	request	createSubjectRequest	M	
response	OA_Subject	M	response	OA_Subject	M	

Table 7: Mapping of parameters used by the createSubject operation

3.2.2 deleteSubject Operation

This subchapter defines the mapping of the deleteSubject operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
subject	OA_Subject	M	request	deleteSubjectRequest	M	

Table 8: Mapping of parameters used by the deleteSubject operation

3.2.3 updateSubject Operation

This subchapter defines the mapping of the updateSubject operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
subject	OA_Subject	M	request	updateSubjectRequest	M	

Table 9: Mapping of parameters used by the updateSubject operation

3.2.4 createGroup Operation

This subchapter defines the mapping of the createGroup operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
groupSubject	OA_Group	M	request	createGroupRequest	M	
response	OA_Group	M	response	OA_Group	M	

Table 10: Mapping of parameters used by the createGroup operation

3.2.5 deleteGroup Operation

This subchapter defines the mapping of the deleteGroup operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
groupSubject	OA_Group	M	request	deleteGroupRequest	M	

Table 11: Mapping of parameters used by the deleteGroup operation

3.2.6 updateGroup Operation

This subchapter defines the mapping of the updateGroup operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
groupSubject	OA_Group	M	request	updateGroupRequest	M	

Table 12: Mapping of parameters used by the updateGroup operation

3.2.7 addPrincipalToGroup Operation

This subchapter defines the mapping of the addPrincipalToGroup operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
principal	OA_Principal	M	request	addPrincipalToGroupRequest	M	
groupSubject	OA_Group	M				

Table 13: Mapping of parameters used by the addPrincipalToGroup operation

3.2.8 removePrincipalFromGroup Operation

This subchapter defines the mapping of the removePrincipalFromGroup operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
Principal	OA_Principal	M	request	removePrincipalFromGroupRequest	M	
group	OA_Group	M				

Table 14: Mapping of parameters used by the removePrincipalFromGroup operation

3.2.9 getSubjects Operation

This subchapter defines the mapping of the getSubjects operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
query	OA_Query	O	request	getSubjectsRequest	M	
response	Sequence<OA_Subject>	M	response	SequenceOfOA_Subject	M	

Table 15: Mapping of parameters used by the getSubjects operation

3.2.10 getGroups Operation

This subchapter defines the mapping of the getGroups operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
query	OA_Query	O	request	getGroupsRequest	M	
response	Se- quence<OA_Group>	M	response	SequenceOfOA_Group	M	

Table 16: Mapping of parameters used by the getGroups operation

3.2.11 addPrincipalToSubject Operation

This subchapter defines the mapping of the addPrincipalToSubject operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
principal	OA_Principal	M	request	addPrincipalToSubjec- tRequest	M	
subject	OA_Subject	M				

Table 17: Mapping of parameters used by the addPrincipalToSubject operation

3.2.12 removePrincipalFromSubject Operation

This subchapter defines the mapping of the removePrincipalFromSubject operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
principal	OA_Principal	M	request	removePrincipalFrom- SubjectRequest	M	
subject	OA_Subject	M				

Table 18: Mapping of parameters used by the removePrincipalFromSubject operation

4 Platform-specific specification

4.1 User Management Service Overview

For a detailed description of the User Management Service Interface refer to the abstract specification of the User Management Service.

The following table lists the operations of the User Management Service and specifies whether they are adapted from another implementation specification.

Name	Overwrite
getCapabilites	Adapted from the specification of the OA Basic Service. Enhanced by service specific capabilities.
createSubject	Copied from the specification of the UserManagement Interface.
deleteSubject	Copied from the specification of the UserManagement Interface.
updateSubject	Copied from the specification of the UserManagement Interface.
createGroup	Copied from the specification of the UserManagement Interface.
deleteGroup	Copied from the specification of the UserManagement Interface.
updateGroup	Copied from the specification of the UserManagement Interface.
addPrincipalToSubject	Copied from the specification of the UserManagement Interface.
addPrincipalToGroup	Copied from the specification of the UserManagement Interface.
getSubjects	Copied from the specification of the UserManagement Interface.
getGroups	Copied from the specification of the UserManagement Interface.
removePrincipalFromSubject	Copied from the specification of the UserManagement Interface.
removePrincipalFromGroup	Copied from the specification of the UserManagement Interface.

Table 19: Summary of Service Operations

The formal platform-specific description of the User Management Service can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

4.2 Specification of a Profile of Parameter Types used by the Authentication Service

The following data types are used within this specification:

Name	Usage	User Defined	from Profile
------	-------	--------------	--------------

ServiceSpecificCapabilities	O	Yes	OA Basic Service
OA_Subject	I/O	Yes	OA Types
OA_Principal	I/O	No	OA Types
OA_SubjectAttributes	I/O	Yes	OA Types
OA_KeyValueSubjectAttributes	I/O	Yes	OA Types
OA_Group	I/O	Yes	OA Types
OA_OSI_Identifier	I/O	No	OA Types
OA_NoSuchMemberException	E	Yes	OA Types/Exceptions Types
OA_ReferentialIntegrityException	E	Yes	OA Types/Exceptions Types
OA_SubjectNotFoundException	E	Yes	OA Types/Exceptions Types
OA_PrincipalNotFoundException	E	Yes	OA Types/Exceptions Types
OA_InvalidParameterValue	E	No	OA Types/Exception Types
OA_MissingParameterValue	E	No	OA Types/Exception Types
OA_NoApplicableCode	E	No	OA Types/Exception Types
OA_InternalError	E	No	OA Types/Exception Types
OA_VersionNegotiationFailed	E	No	OA Types/Exception Types

Table 20: XML Types

The formal specification in XML of these types can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

This service specification does not define user defined Types.

4.3 Specification of the getCapabilities Operation

The mandatory getCapabilities operation informs the client of the capabilities of an ORCHESTRA Service Instance (OSI). This operation takes into account that in addition to capabilities that are common to all ORCHESTRA Services an ORCHESTRA Service may provide a specific set of capabilities. Furthermore, this operation allows the capabilities to be delivered according to different service meta-information schemas. This implementation specification therefore does not prescribe a certain schema to be used for the service capabilities. One or several schemas to be supported as well as a default schema have to be defined in the context of an OSN.

A service meta-information document is returned to the requesting client, either complete or including selected parts according to the given sections in the request.

A request to perform the getCapabilities operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 11. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional | mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the “Description” shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although some values listed in the “Name” column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	modified			
Overrides	not applicable			
Preconditions	none			
Post conditions	Service meta-information document returned to requesting client, either complete or including selected parts according to the given sections in the request			
Use	mandatory			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	OA_GetCapabilitiesRequest	mandatory	Specifies the parts of the meta-information to be returned. If absent, all parts shall be returned using the default schema.
Returns	Type		Description	
	OA_CapabilitiesDocument		Service capabilities of the specific OSI for the specific ORCHESTRA Service.	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value. Return the name of the parameter with invalid value.	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value. Return the name of the missing parameter	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	

	OA_InternalError	A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)
	OA_VersionNegotiationFailed	List of versions in acceptSpecVersions parameter value in the getCapabilities request did not include any version supported by the OSI.
	OA_UnsupportedSchema	The sections parameter in the getCapabilities request referred to a schema unsupported by the OSI.

Table 21: Specification of the getCapabilities Operation

Note that in contrast to the abstract specification the request parameter is mandatory in order to simplify the mapping to the platform.

According to the abstract specification the request parameter consists of the following elements:

- **acceptFormats:** Optional parameter containing a prioritized sequence of zero or more response formats desired by the caller, with preferred formats listed first. The formats are to be expressed in terms of MIME types. Independent of the contents of this element, the returned capabilities can always be formatted according to the default MIME type which is defined as "text/xml".
- **acceptSpecVersions:** Optional parameter containing a prioritized sequence of zero or more specification versions of the ORCHESTRA service accepted by the client, with the preferred versions listed first. If no versions are included in the request, the highest version that the service supports shall be used.
- **sections:** Optional parameter specifying the schema for service meta-information according to which the capabilities shall be structured. In addition the names of requested sections in the complete set of meta-information elements can be listed. If absent, the complete service capabilities shall be returned structured according to a default schema which has to be defined in the context of an OSN.

According to the abstract specification the return parameter consists of the following elements:

- **capabilitySections:** Capabilities as meta-information document which is internally structured according to the indicated format and the indicated schema. It is either complete or includes only selected parts according to the given sections in the request.
- **format:** MIME type of the format in which the capabilities are returned as value of the capabilitySections parameter. The value of this attribute may always denote the default MIME Type "text/xml" indicating that the capabilities are formatted in XML.
- **schemaName:** Schema according to which the capabilities are returned. The value is the same as the one contained in the sections parameter of the request. If not explicitly included in the request, the value indicates the default schema.
- **version:** Version number of the specification to which the delivered service meta-information document is conform.

The formal platform-specific specification of the getCapabilities operation can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

```
<wsdl:message name="getCapabilitiesRequest">
  <wsdl:part name="request" element="oab:OA_GetCapabilitiesRequest"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="getCapabilitiesResponse">
  <wsdl:part name="return" element="oab:OA_GetCapabilitiesResponse"/>
</wsdl:message>
```

4.4 Specification of the createSubject Operation

The mandatory createSubject operation is used to add new subjects to a User Management Service instance.

A request to perform the createSubject operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 22. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional|mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the “Description” shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although some values listed in the “Name” column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	Identical			
Overrides	Not applicable			
Preconditions	None			
Post conditions	None			
Use	Mandatory			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	createSubjectRequest	mandatory	It contains the OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType and the OA_SubjectType
Returns	Type		Description	
	OA_Subject		The created subject including a recently added unique id (unique within the service) that can be used for a latter reference to this subject.	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value.	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value.	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	
	OA_InternalError		A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)	
	OA_PermissionDeniedException		The service requestor does not have permissions needed to perform the requested operation.	

Table 22: Specification of the createSubject Operation

The formal platform-specific specification of the createSubject operation can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

Implementation Specification of the User Management Service – Specification of the createSubject Operation


```
<wsdl:message name="createSubjectRequest">
  <wsdl:part name="newUser" element="ums_requests:createSubjectRequest"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="createSubjectResponse">
  <wsdl:part name="return" element="ums_types:OA_Subject"/>
</wsdl:message>
```

4.5 Specification of the deleteSubject Operation

The mandatory deleteSubject operation is used to delete subjects from a UserManagement Service instance.

Deleting a subject means to completely remove it from the OSN. This includes to delete the subject from the correspondent UserManagement Instance, as well as the update of all principals currently member of it.

A request to perform the deleteSubject operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 23. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional|mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the “Description” shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although some values listed in the “Name” column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	Identical			
Overrides	Not applicable			
Preconditions	Subject to be deleted exists			
Post conditions	Subject is removed and all principals, prior member of this subject, are updated.			
Use	mandatory			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	deleteSubjectRequest	mandatory	It contains the OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType and the OA_SubjectType
Returns	Type		Description	
	None		None	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value.	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value.	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	
	OA_InternalError		A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)	
	OA_ReferentialIntegrityException		Thrown if at least one subject related feature (e.g. a principal) cannot be deleted.	
	OA_SubjectNotFoundException		Thrown if the subject to be deleted does not exist.	
	OA_PermissionDeniedException		The service requestor does not have permissions needed to perform the requested operation.	

Table 23: Specification of the deleteSubject Operation

The formal platform-specific specification of the deleteSubject operation can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

```
<wsdl:message name="deleteSubjectRequest">  
  <wsdl:part name="user" element="ums_requests:deleteSubjectRequest"/>  
</wsdl:message>
```

4.6 Specification of the updateSubject Operation

The mandatory updateSubject operation is used to update subjects as well as related information like subject attributes from a User Management Service instance.

A request to perform the updateSubject operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 24. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional|mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the “Description” shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although some values listed in the “Name” column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	Identical			
Overrides	not applicable			
Preconditions	Subject to be updated exists			
Post conditions	none			
Use	mandatory			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	updateSubjectRequest	mandatory	It contains the OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType and the OA_SubjectType
Returns	Type		Description	
	None		None	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value.	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value.	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	
	OA_InternalError		A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)	
	OA_SubjectNotFoundException		Thrown if the subject to be updated does not exist.	
	OA_PermissionDeniedException		The service requestor does not have permissions needed to perform the requested operation.	

Table 24: Specification of the updateSubject Operation

The formal platform-specific specification of the updateSubject operation can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

```
<wsdl:message name="updateSubjectRequest">
```

Implementation Specification of the User Management Service –
Specification of the updateSubject Operation


```
<wsdl:part name="user" element="ums_requests:updateSubjectRequest" />  
</wsdl:message>
```

4.7 Specification of the createGroup Operation

The mandatory operation is used to create new group subjects in a UserManagement Service instance. Members of a group are principals not subjects.

As groups themselves are special subjects, they can have one or more principals on their own.

Again, groups have two associations to principals. First, members of groups are principals. Second, groups have principals like ordinary subjects. The latter is needed that a service provider may grant permissions to a group. Since permissions are generally bound to principals, they can also be bound to group principals.

A request to perform the createGroup operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 25. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional|mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the “Description” shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although some values listed in the “Name” column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	Identical			
Overrides	not applicable			
Preconditions	None			
Post conditions	Principals have to be added.			
Use	mandatory			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	createGroupRequest	mandatory	It contains the OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType and the OA_GroupType
Returns	Type		Description	
	OA_Group		The created group including a recently added id (unique within the service) that can be used for a latter reference to this group.	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value.	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value. Return the name of the missing parameter.	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	
	OA_InternalError		A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)	
	OA_PermissionDeniedException		The service requestor does not have permissions needed to perform the requested operation.	

Table 25: Specification of the createGroup Operation

The formal platform-specific specification of the createGroup operation can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

```
<wsdl:message name="createGroupRequest">
  <wsdl:part name="newGroup" element="ums_requests:createGroupRequest"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="createGroupResponse">
  <wsdl:part name="return" element="ums_types:OA_Group"/>
</wsdl:message>
```

4.8 Specification of the deleteGroup Operation

The mandatory deleteGroup operation is used to delete group subjects in a UserManagement Service instance.

Deletion affects only the group's own principals and the membership of added user principals. No principals of members are deleted.

A request to perform the deleteGroup operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 26. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional|mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the "Description" shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although some values listed in the "Name" column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	Identical			
Overrides	Not applicable			
Preconditions	Group must exist			
Post conditions	none			
Use	mandatory			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	deleteGroupRequest	mandatory	It contains the OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType and the OA_GroupType
Returns	Type		Description	
	None		None	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value.	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value.	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	
	OA_InternalError		A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)	
	OA_SubjectNotFoundException		Thrown if the group subject to be deleted does not exist.	
	OA_PermissionDeniedException		The service requestor does not have permissions needed to perform the requested operation.	

Table 26: Specification of the deleteGroup Operation

The formal platform-specific specification of the deleteGroup operation can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

```
<wsdl:message name="deleteGroupRequest">  
  <wsdl:part name="group" element="ums_requests:deleteGroupRequest"/>  
</wsdl:message>
```

4.9 Specification of the updateGroup Operation

The mandatory updateGroup operation is used to update group subjects in a User Management Service instance.

A request to perform the updateGroup operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 27. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional|mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the “Description” shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although some values listed in the “Name” column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	Identical			
Overrides	not applicable			
Preconditions	Group has to exist.			
Post conditions	none			
Use	mandatory			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	updateGroupRequest	mandatory	It contains the OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType and the OA_GroupType
Returns	Type		Description	
	None		None	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value.	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	
	OA_InternalError		A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)	
	OA_SubjectNotFoundException		Group to be updated does not exist.	
	OA_PermissionDeniedException		The service requestor does not have permissions needed to perform the requested operation.	

Table 27: Specification of the updateGroup Operation

The formal platform-specific specification of the updateGroup operation can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

```
<wsdl:message name="updateGroupRequest">
```

Implementation Specification of the User Management Service –
Specification of the updateGroup Operation


```
<wsdl:part name="group" element="ums_requests:updateGroupRequest"/>  
</wsdl:message>
```

4.10 Specification of the addPrincipalToGroup Operation

The mandatory addPrincipalToGroup operation is used to add an existing principal to a group subject in an User Management Service instance. The principal can be part of any Orchestra Authentication Service instance.

A request to perform the addPrincipalToGroup operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 28. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional|mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the “Description” shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although some values listed in the “Name” column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	Identical			
Overrides	not applicable			
Preconditions	Group has to exist. Principal has to exist			
Post conditions	Principal may not be deleted without notification of the User Management Service Instance containing the group.			
Use	mandatory			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	addPrincipalToGroupRequest	mandatory	It contains the OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType, the OA_PrincipalType and the OA_GroupType
Returns	Type		Description	
	None		None	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value.	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value.	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	
	OA_InternalError		A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)	
	OA_SubjectNotFoundExpection		Group does not exist.	
	OA_PrincipalNotFoundExpection		Principal to be added to the group does not exist.	
	OA_PermissionDeniedExpection		The service requestor does not have permissions needed to perform the requested operation.	

Table 28: Specification of the addPrincipalToGroup Operation

The formal platform-specific specification of the addPrincipalToGroup operation can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

```
<wsdl:message name="addPrincipalToGroupRequest">  
  <wsdl:part name="principalAndGroup"  
    element="ums_requests:addPrincipalToGroupRequest" />  
</wsdl:message>
```

4.11 Specification of the removePrincipalFromGroup Operation

The mandatory removePrincipalFromGroup operation is used to remove an existing principal from an existing group subject in a User Management Service instance. The principal can be part of any Orchestra Authentication Service instance. The principal itself gets not deleted.

A request to perform the removePrincipalFromgroup operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 29. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional|mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the “Description” shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although some values listed in the “Name” column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	Identical			
Overrides	not applicable			
Preconditions	Group has to exist. Principal has to exist. Principal has to be member of the group.			
Post conditions	None			
Use	mandatory			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	removePrincipal-FromGroupRequest	mandatory	It contains the OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType, the OA_PrincipalType and the OA_GroupType
Returns	Type		Description	
	None		None	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value.	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value.	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	
	OA_InternalError		A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)	
	OA_SubjectNotFoundExpection		Group does not exist.	
	OA_PrincipalNotFoundExpection		Principal to be added to the group does not exist.	
	OA_NoSuchMemberExpection		Principal to be removed is not a member of the given group.	

	OA_PermissionDeniedException	The service requestor does not have permissions needed to perform the requested operation.
--	------------------------------	--

Table 29: Specification of the removePrincipalFromGroup Operation

The formal platform-specific specification of the removePrincipalFromGroup operation can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

```
<wsdl:message name="removePrincipalFromGroupRequest">  
  <wsdl:part name="principalAndGroup"  
    element="ums_requests:removePrincipalFromGroupRequest"/>  
</wsdl:message>
```

4.12 Specification of the getSubjects Operation

The mandatory getSubjects operation is used to retrieve specified subjects from an UserManagement Service instance.

A request to perform the getSubjects operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 30. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional|mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the “Description” shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although some values listed in the “Name” column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	Identical			
Overrides	not applicable			
Preconditions	none			
Post conditions	none			
Use	mandatory			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	getSubjectsRequest	mandatory	It contains the OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType and the OA_Query
Returns	Type		Description	
	SequenceOfOA_Subject		A list of subjects selected by the given query.	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value.	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value.	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	
	OA_InternalError		A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)	
	OA_SubjectNotFoundException		No subjects match the query..	
	OA_PermissionDeniedException		The service requestor does not have permissions needed to perform the requested operation.	

Table 30: Specification of the getSubjects Operation

The formal platform-specific specification of the getSubjects operation can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

Implementation Specification of the User Management Service – Specification of the getSubjects Operation


```
<wsdl:message name="getSubjectsRequest">
  <wsdl:part name="query" element="ums_requests:getSubjectsRequest"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="getSubjectsResponse">
  <wsdl:part name="return" element="ums_types:SequenceOfOA_Subject"/>
</wsdl:message>
```

4.13 Specification of the getGroups Operation

The mandatory getGroups operation is used to retrieve specified groups from an UserManagement Service instance.

A request to perform the getGroups operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 31. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional|mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the “Description” shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although some values listed in the “Name” column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	Identical			
Overrides	not applicable			
Preconditions	none			
Post conditions	none			
Use	mandatory			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	getGroupsRequest	mandatory	It contains the OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType and the OA_Query
Returns	Type		Description	
	SequenceOfOA_Group		A list of groups selected by the given query.	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value.	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value.	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	
	OA_InternalError		A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)	
	OA_SubjectNotFoundException		No subjects match the query..	
	OA_PermissionDeniedException		The service requestor does not have permissions needed to perform the requested operation.	

Table 31: Specification of the getGroups Operation

The formal platform-specific specification of the getGroups operation can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

```
<wsdl:message name="getGroupsRequest">  
  <wsdl:part name="query" element="ums_requests:getGroupsRequest" />  
</wsdl:message>  
<wsdl:message name="getGroupsResponse">  
  <wsdl:part name="return" element="ums_types:SequenceOfOA_Group" />  
</wsdl:message>
```

4.14 Specification of the addPrincipalToSubject Operation

The mandatory addPrincipalToSubject operation is used to add an existing principal to an existing subject in an UserManagement Service instance. The principal can be part of any Orchestra Authentication Service instance.

Note that a group is also a subject. Thus, this operation can also be used to add principals to a group. This operation cannot be used to add principals as a member to a group.

A request to perform the addPrincipalToSubject operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 32. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional|mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the “Description” shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although some values listed in the “Name” column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	Identical			
Overrides	not applicable			
Preconditions	Subject has to exist. Principal has to exist.			
Post conditions	Principal may not be deleted without notification of the User Management Service instance containing the group.			
Use	mandatory			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	addPrincipalToSubjectRequest	mandatory	It contains the OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType, the OA_PrincipalType and the OA_SubjectType
Returns	Type		Description	
	None		None	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value.	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value.	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	
	OA_InternalError		A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)	
	OA_SubjectNotFoundExpection		Group does not exist.	
	OA_PrincipalNotFoundExpection		Principal to be added to the group does not exist.	

	OA_PermissionDeniedException	The service requestor does not have permissions needed to perform the requested operation.
--	------------------------------	--

Table 32: Specification of the addPrincipalToSubject Operation

The formal platform-specific specification of the addPrincipalToSubject operation can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

```
<wsdl:message name="addPrincipalToSubjectRequest">  
  <wsdl:part name="principalAndSubject"  
    element="ums_requests:addPrincipalToSubjectRequest" />  
</wsdl:message>
```

4.15 Specification of the removePrincipalFromSubject Operation

The mandatory removePrincipalFromSubject operation is used to remove a principal from a subject in an User Management Service instance. The principal can be part of any Orchestra Authentication Service instance.

Note that a group is also a subject. Thus, this operation can also be used to remove principals from a group. This operation cannot be used to remove member principals from a group.

A request to perform the removePrincipalFromSubject operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 33. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional|mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the “Description” shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although some values listed in the “Name” column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	Identical			
Overrides	not applicable			
Preconditions	Association between given subject and principal has to exist.			
Post conditions	Association between given subject and principal has been removed.			
Use	mandatory			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	removePrincipalFromSubjectRequest	mandatory	It contains the OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType, the OA_PrincipalType and the OA_SubjectType
Returns	Type		Description	
	None		None	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value.	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value.	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	
	OA_InternalError		A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)	
	OA_SubjectNotFoundException		Group does not exist.	
	OA_PrincipalNotFoundException		Principal to be added to the group does not exist.	

	OA_PermissionDeniedException	The service requestor does not have permissions needed to perform the requested operation.
--	------------------------------	--

Table 33: Specification of the removePrincipalFromSubject Operation

The formal platform-specific specification of the removePrincipalFromSubject operation can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

```
<wsdl:message name="removePrincipalFromSubjectRequest">  
  <wsdl:part name="principalAndSubject"  
    element="ums_requests:removePrincipalFromSubjectRequest"/>  
</wsdl:message>
```

5 Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents

5.1 XML Schema Documents

The following XML Schema Documents define the data types of this service.

The XML schema documents of the used data types are bundled in a zip file with the present document and can be downloaded at https://portal.opengeospatial.org/files/?artifact_id=20057.

In addition to XML Schema Documents specified in this appendix, this specification requires several normative XML Schema Documents. These XML Schema Documents define the common data types, e.g. common Exception Types, Basic Data Types and the GML Profile.

This file contains the XML Schema documents of the OA Basic Service and Authentication Service.

The namespaces

<http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/OABasicService/types/1.0>,

<http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/OABasicService/exceptions/1.0>,

<http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthenticationService/types/1.0> are used.

5.1.1 usermanagement_exceptions.xsd

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="windows-1252"?>
<schema xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
  xmlns:ums_exc="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/UserManagementService/exceptions/1.0"
  xmlns:oab_exc="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/OABasicService/exceptions/1.0"
  targetNamespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/UserManagementService/exceptions/1.0"
  elementFormDefault="qualified"
  version="1.0">
  <!--XML Schema document created by ShapeChange-->
  <element name="OA_ReferentialIntegrityException"
    type="ums_exc:OA_ReferentialIntegrityExceptionType"
    substitutionGroup="oab_exc:OA_AbstractException"/>
  <complexType name="OA_ReferentialIntegrityExceptionType">
    <complexContent>
      <extension base="oab_exc:OA_AbstractException">
        <sequence/>
      </extension>
    </complexContent>
  </complexType>
  <complexType name="OA_ReferentialIntegrityExceptionPropertyType">
    <sequence minOccurs="0">
      <element ref="ums_exc:OA_ReferentialIntegrityException"/>
    </sequence>
    <!-- attributeGroup ref="xlink:simpleLink"/ -->
  </complexType>
  <element name="OA_NoSuchMemberException"
```

```
        type="ums_exc:OA_NoSuchMemberExceptionType"
        substitutionGroup="oab_exc:OA_AbstractException" />
<complexType name="OA_NoSuchMemberExceptionType">
  <complexContent>
    <extension base="oab_exc:OA_AbstractException">
      <sequence/>
    </extension>
  </complexContent>
</complexType>
<complexType name="OA_NoSuchMemberExceptionPropertyType">
  <sequence minOccurs="0">
    <element ref="ums_exc:OA_NoSuchMemberException" />
  </sequence>
  <!-- attributeGroup ref="xlink:simpleLink" / -->
</complexType>
<element name="OA_SubjectNotFoundException"
  type="ums_exc:OA_SubjectNotFoundExceptionType"
  substitutionGroup="oab_exc:OA_AbstractException" />
<complexType name="OA_SubjectNotFoundExceptionType">
  <complexContent>
    <extension base="oab_exc:OA_AbstractException">
      <sequence/>
    </extension>
  </complexContent>
</complexType>
<complexType name="OA_SubjectNotFoundExceptionPropertyType">
  <sequence minOccurs="0">
    <element ref="ums_exc:OA_SubjectNotFoundException" />
  </sequence>
  <!-- attributeGroup ref="xlink:simpleLink" / -->
</complexType>
</schema>
```

5.1.2 usermanagement_types.xsd

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="windows-1252"?>
<schema xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
  xmlns:ums_types="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/UserManagementService/types/1.0"
  xmlns:authen_types="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthenticationService/types/1.0"
  elementFormDefault="qualified"
  targetNamespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/UserManagementService/types/1.0"
  version="1.0">
  <element name="OA_ServiceChainSubject" substitutionGroup="ums_types:OA_ServiceSubject"
    type="ums_types:OA_ServiceChainSubjectType"/>
  <complexType name="OA_ServiceChainSubjectType">
    <complexContent>
      <extension base="ums_types:OA_ServiceSubjectType">
        <sequence/>
      </extension>
    </complexContent>
  </complexType>
  <complexType name="OA_ServiceChainSubjectPropertyType">
    <sequence minOccurs="0">
      <element ref="ums_types:OA_ServiceChainSubject"/>
    </sequence>
    <!-- attributeGroup ref="xlink:simpleLink"/ -->
  </complexType>
  <element name="OA_Group" substitutionGroup="ums_types:OA_Subject"
    type="ums_types:OA_GroupType"/>
  <complexType name="OA_GroupType">
    <annotation>
      <documentation>
        A "OA_Group" is a specialisation of an "OA_Subject", therefore it can authenticate a
        principal, thereafter authorisations take place with authenticated principals.
        A group consists of principals (as members).</documentation>
      </annotation>
    <complexContent>
      <extension base="ums_types:OA_SubjectType">
        <sequence>
          <element name="memberPrincipals">
            <complexType>
              <sequence>
                <element name="Sequence">
                  <complexType>
                    <sequence>
                      <element maxOccurs="unbounded" minOccurs="0" name="element"
                        type="authen_types:OA_PrincipalPropertyType"/>
                    </sequence>
                  </complexType>
                </element>
              </sequence>
            </complexType>
          </element>
        </sequence>
      </extension>
    </complexContent>
  </complexType>
</schema>
```

```
        </sequence>
      </complexType>
    </element>
  </sequence>
</complexType>
</element>
</sequence>
</extension>
</complexContent>
</complexType>
<complexType name="OA_GroupPropertyType">
  <sequence minOccurs="0">
    <element ref="ums_types:OA_Group"/>
  </sequence>
  <!-- attributeGroup ref="xlink:simpleLink"/ -->
</complexType>
<element name="OA_KeyValuePair" type="ums_types:OA_KeyValuePairType"/>
<complexType name="OA_KeyValuePairType">
  <sequence>
    <element name="key" type="string"/>
    <element name="value" type="string"/>
  </sequence>
</complexType>
<complexType name="OA_KeyValuePairPropertyType">
  <sequence minOccurs="0">
    <element ref="ums_types:OA_KeyValuePair"/>
  </sequence>
  <!-- attributeGroup ref="xlink:simpleLink"/ -->
</complexType>

<element name="OA_ServiceSubject" substitutionGroup="ums_types:OA_Subject"
  type="ums_types:OA_ServiceSubjectType"/>
<complexType name="OA_ServiceSubjectType">
  <complexContent>
    <extension base="ums_types:OA_SubjectType">
      <sequence/>
    </extension>
  </complexContent>
</complexType>
<complexType name="OA_ServiceSubjectPropertyType">
  <sequence minOccurs="0">
    <element ref="ums_types:OA_ServiceSubject"/>
  </sequence>
```

```
<!-- attributeGroup ref="xlink:simpleLink" / -->
</complexType>
<element name="OA_SubjectAttributes" type="ums_types:OA_SubjectAttributesType"/>
<complexType name="OA_SubjectAttributesType">
  <sequence/>
</complexType>
<complexType name="OA_SubjectAttributesPropertyType">
  <sequence minOccurs="0">
    <element ref="ums_types:OA_SubjectAttributes"/>
  </sequence>
  <!-- attributeGroup ref="xlink:simpleLink" / -->
</complexType>
<element name="OA_Subject" type="ums_types:OA_SubjectType"/>
<complexType name="OA_SubjectType">
  <sequence>
    <element name="id" type="integer"/>
    <element name="origin" type="string"/>
    <element name="principals">
      <complexType>
        <sequence>
          <element name="Sequence">
            <complexType>
              <sequence>
                <element minOccurs="unbounded" minOccurs="0" name="element"
                  type="ums_types:OA_PrincipalPropertyType"/>
              </sequence>
            </complexType>
          </element>
        </sequence>
      </complexType>
    </element>
    <complexType name="OA_SubjectPropertyType">
      <sequence minOccurs="0">
        <element ref="ums_types:OA_Subject"/>
      </sequence>
    </complexType>
  <!-- attributeGroup ref="xlink:simpleLink" / -->
</complexType>
<element name="OA_KeyValueSubjectAttributes"
  substitutionGroup="ums_types:OA_SubjectAttributes"
  type="ums_types:OA_KeyValueSubjectAttributesType"/>
<complexType name="OA_KeyValueSubjectAttributesType">
```



```

<complexContent>
  <extension base="ums_types:OA_SubjectAttributesType">
    <sequence>
      <element name="attributes">
        <complexType>
          <sequence>
            <element name="Set">
              <complexType>
                <sequence>
                  <element maxOccurs="unbounded" minOccurs="0" name="element"
                    type="ums_types:OA_KeyValuePairPropertyType"/>
                </sequence>
              </complexType>
            </element>
          </sequence>
        </complexType>
      </element>
    </sequence>
  </extension>
</complexContent>
</complexType>
<complexType name="OA_KeyValueSubjectAttributesPropertyType">
  <sequence minOccurs="0">
    <element ref="ums_types:OA_KeyValueSubjectAttributes"/>
  </sequence>
  <!-- attributeGroup ref="xlink:simpleLink" / -->
</complexType>
<element name="SequenceOfOA_Subject" type="ums_types:SequenceOfOA_SubjectType"/>
<complexType name="SequenceOfOA_SubjectType">
  <sequence>
    <element name="Subjects">
      <complexType>
        <sequence>
          <element name="Sequence">
            <complexType>
              <sequence>
                <element name="Element"
                  type="ums_types:OA_SubjectPropertyType"
                  minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/>
              </sequence>
            </complexType>
          </element>
        </sequence>
      </complexType>
    </element>
  </sequence>
</complexType>

```

```
        </element>
    </sequence>
</complexType>
    <complexType name="SequenceOfOA_SubjectPropertyType">
        <sequence minOccurs="0">
            <element ref="ums_types:SequenceOfOA_Subject" />
        </sequence>
        <!-- attributeGroup ref="xlink:simpleLink" / -->
    </complexType>

    <element name="SequenceOfOA_Group" type="ums_types:SequenceOfOA_GroupType" />
<complexType name="SequenceOfOA_GroupType">
    <sequence>
        <element name="Groups">
            <complexType>
                <sequence>
                    <element name="Sequence">
                        <complexType>
                            <sequence>
                                <element name="Element"
                                    type="ums_types:OA_GroupPropertyType" mi-
                                    nOccurs="0"
                                    maxOccurs="unbounded" />
                            </sequence>
                        </complexType>
                    </element>
                </sequence>
            </complexType>
        </element>
    </sequence>
</complexType>
</element>
</sequence>
</complexType>
    <complexType name="SequenceOfOA_GroupPropertyType">
        <sequence minOccurs="0">
            <element ref="ums_types:SequenceOfOA_Group" />
        </sequence>
        <!-- attributeGroup ref="xlink:simpleLink" / -->
    </complexType>
</schema>
```

5.1.3 usermanagement_requests.xsd

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="windows-1252"?>
<schema xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
  xmlns:gml="http://www.opengis.net/gml"
  xmlns:ums_types="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/UserManagementService/types/1.0"
  xmlns:authen_types="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthenticationService/types/1.0"
  xmlns:ums_requests="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/UserManagementService/requests/1.0"
  xmlns:oas="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/OABasicService/types/1.0"
  targetNamespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/UserManagementService/requests/1.0"
  elementFormDefault="qualified"
  version="1.0">
  <element name="createSubjectRequest" type="ums_requests:createSubjectRequest" />
  <complexType name="createSubjectRequest">
    <sequence>
      <element name="sessionInformation"
        type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType" />
      <element name="newUser" type="ums_types:OA_SubjectType" />
    </sequence>
  </complexType>
  <element name="deleteSubjectRequest" type="ums_requests:deleteSubjectRequest" />
  <complexType name="deleteSubjectRequest">
    <sequence>
      <element name="sessionInformation"
        type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType" />
      <element name="user" type="ums_types:OA_SubjectType" />
    </sequence>
  </complexType>
  <element name="updateSubjectRequest" type="ums_requests:updateSubjectRequest" />
  <complexType name="updateSubjectRequest">
    <sequence>
      <element name="sessionInformation"
        type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType" />
      <element name="user" type="ums_types:OA_SubjectType" />
    </sequence>
  </complexType>
  <element name="createGroupRequest" type="ums_requests:createGroupRequest" />
  <complexType name="createGroupRequest">
    <sequence>
      <element name="sessionInformation"
        type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType" />
      <element name="oagroup" type="ums_types:OA_GroupType" />
    </sequence>
  </complexType>
</schema>
```

```
</complexType>
<element name="deleteGroupRequest" type="ums_requests:deleteGroupRequest"/>
<complexType name="deleteGroupRequest">
  <sequence>
    <element name="sessionInformation"
      type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType"/>
    <element name="oagroup" type="ums_types:OA_GroupType"/>
  </sequence>
</complexType>
<element name="updateGroupRequest" type="ums_requests:updateGroupRequest"/>
<complexType name="updateGroupRequest">
  <sequence>
    <element name="sessionInformation"
      type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType"/>
    <element name="oagroup" type="ums_types:OA_GroupType"/>
  </sequence>
</complexType>
<element name="getSubjectsRequest" type="ums_requests:getSubjectsRequest"/>
<complexType name="getSubjectsRequest">
  <sequence>
    <element name="sessionInformation"
      type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType"/>
    <element name="query" type="oas:OA_Query"/>
  </sequence>
</complexType>
<element name="getGroupsRequest" type="ums_requests:getGroupsRequest"/>
<complexType name="getGroupsRequest">
  <sequence>
    <element name="sessionInformation"
      type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType"/>
    <element name="query" type="oas:OA_Query"/>
  </sequence>
</complexType>
<element name="addPrincipalToSubjectRequest"
  type="ums_requests:addPrincipalToSubjectRequest"/>
<complexType name="addPrincipalToSubjectRequest">
  <sequence>
    <element name="sessionInformation"
      type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType"/>
    <element name="oapincipal" type="authen_types:OA_PrincipalType"/>
    <element name="oasubject" type="ums_types:OA_SubjectType"/>
  </sequence>
</complexType>
<element name="addPrincipalToGroupRequest"
```

```
        type="ums_requests:addPrincipalToGroupRequest" />
<complexType name="addPrincipalToGroupRequest">
  <sequence>
    <element name="sessionInformation"
      type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType" />
    <element name="oapincipal" type="authen_types:OA_PrincipalType" />
    <element name="oagroup" type="ums_types:OA_GroupType" />
  </sequence>
</complexType>
<element name="removePrincipalFromGroupRequest"
  type="ums_requests:removePrincipalFromGroupRequest" />
<complexType name="removePrincipalFromGroupRequest">
  <sequence>
    <element name="sessionInformation"
      type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType" />
    <element name="oapincipal" type="authen_types:OA_PrincipalType" />
    <element name="oagroup" type="ums_types:OA_GroupType" />
  </sequence>
</complexType>
<element name="removePrincipalFromSubjectRequest"
  type="ums_requests:removePrincipalFromSubjectRequest" />
<complexType name="removePrincipalFromSubjectRequest">
  <sequence>
    <element name="sessionInformation"
      type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType" />
    <element name="oapincipal" type="authen_types:OA_PrincipalType" />
    <element name="oasubject" type="ums_types:OA_SubjectType" />
  </sequence>
</complexType>
</schema>
```

5.2 WSDL Document

The following WSDL Version 1.1 document is the formal specification of the User Management Service according to rules of the “ORCHESTRA Web Services Platform”. It defines the mandatory SOAP binding.

The WSDL document is bundled in a zip file with the present document and can be downloaded at https://portal.opengeospatial.org/files/?artifact_id=20057.

```
<?xml version="1.0"?>
<wsdl:definitions xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
    xmlns:soap="http://schemas.xmlsoap.org/wsdl/soap/"
    xmlns:http="http://schemas.xmlsoap.org/wsdl/http/"
    xmlns:mime="http://schemas.xmlsoap.org/wsdl/mime/"
    xmlns:wsdl="http://schemas.xmlsoap.org/wsdl/"
    xmlns:ums="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/UserManagementService"
    xmlns:ums_exc="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/UserManagementService/exceptions/1.0"
    xmlns:ums_oami="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/UserManagementService/oami/1.0"
    xmlns:ums_types="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/UserManagementService/types/1.0"
    xmlns:authen_exc="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthenticationService/exceptions/1.0"
    xmlns:author_exc="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthorisationService/exceptions/1.0"
    xmlns:ums_requests="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/UserManagementService/requests/1.0"
    xmlns:oab_exc="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/OABasicService/exceptions/1.0"
    xmlns:oab_types="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/OABasicService/types/1.0"
    name="WSDLComponent1"
    targetNamespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/UserManagementService">
<wsdl:types>
    <xs:schema targetNamespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/UserManagementService"
        xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" elementFormDefault="qualified"
        attributeFormDefault="qualified">
        <xs:import
            namespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/UserManagementService/requests/1.0"
            schemaLocation="usermanagement_requests.xsd"/>
        <xs:import
            namespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthorisationService/exceptions/1.0"
            schemaLocation="authorisation_exceptions.xsd"/>
        <xs:import
            namespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/OABasicService/exceptions/1.0"
            schemaLocation="oa_basic_ex.xsd"/>
        <xs:import
            namespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/UserManagementService/exceptions/1.0"
            schemaLocation="usermanagement_exceptions.xsd"/>
        <xs:import
            namespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthenticationService/exceptions/1.0"
            schemaLocation="authentication_exceptions.xsd"/>
    </xs:schema>
</wsdl:types>
</wsdl:definitions>
```

```
<xs:import
  namespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/UserManagementService/types/1.0"
  schemaLocation="usermanagement_types.xsd"/>
<xs:import namespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/OABasicService/types/1.0"
  schemaLocation="oa_basic.xsd"/>
<xs:import namespace="http://eu-
orchestra.org/OA/OABasicService/exceptions/1.0"
  schemaLocation="oa_basic_ex.xsd"/>
<xs:import namespace="http://eu-
orchestra.org/OA/AuthenticationService/types/1.0"
  schemaLocation="authentication_types.xsd"/>
<xs:import namespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/basicTypes/1.0"
  schemaLocation="basic_types.xsd"/>
</xs:schema>
</wSDL:types>
<wSDL:message name="getCapabilitiesRequest">
  <wSDL:part name="oaCapabilitiesRequest"
    element="oab_types:OA_GetCapabilitiesRequest"/>
</wSDL:message>
<wSDL:message name="getCapabilitiesResponse">
  <wSDL:part name="oaCapabilitiesResponse"
    element="oab_types:OA_GetCapabilitiesResponse"/>
</wSDL:message>
<wSDL:message name="createSubjectRequest">
  <wSDL:part name="newUser" element="ums_requests:createSubjectRequest"/>
</wSDL:message>
<wSDL:message name="createSubjectResponse">
  <wSDL:part name="return" element="ums_types:OA_Subject"/>
</wSDL:message>
<wSDL:message name="deleteSubjectRequest">
  <wSDL:part name="user" element="ums_requests:deleteSubjectRequest"/>
</wSDL:message>
<wSDL:message name="updateSubjectRequest">
  <wSDL:part name="user" element="ums_requests:updateSubjectRequest"/>
</wSDL:message>
<wSDL:message name="createGroupRequest">
  <wSDL:part name="newGroup" element="ums_requests:createGroupRequest"/>
</wSDL:message>
<wSDL:message name="createGroupResponse">
  <wSDL:part name="return" element="ums_types:OA_Group"/>
</wSDL:message>
<wSDL:message name="deleteGroupRequest">
  <wSDL:part name="group" element="ums_requests:deleteGroupRequest"/>
</wSDL:message>
```

```
<wsdl:message name="updateGroupRequest">
    <wsdl:part name="group" element="ums_requests:updateGroupRequest"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="getSubjectsRequest">
    <wsdl:part name="query" element="ums_requests:getSubjectsRequest"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="getSubjectsResponse">
    <wsdl:part name="return" element="ums_types:SequenceOfOA_Subject"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="getGroupsRequest">
    <wsdl:part name="query" element="ums_requests:getGroupsRequest"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="getGroupsResponse">
    <wsdl:part name="return" element="ums_types:SequenceOfOA_Group"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="addPrincipalToSubjectRequest">
    <wsdl:part name="principalAndSubject"
        element="ums_requests:addPrincipalToSubjectRequest"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="addPrincipalToGroupRequest">
    <wsdl:part name="principalAndGroup"
        element="ums_requests:addPrincipalToGroupRequest"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="removePrincipalFromGroupRequest">
    <wsdl:part name="principalAndGroup"
        element="ums_requests:removePrincipalFromGroupRequest"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="removePrincipalFromSubjectRequest">
    <wsdl:part name="principalAndSubject"
        element="ums_requests:removePrincipalFromSubjectRequest"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="InvalidParameterValueFault">
    <wsdl:part name="OA_InvalidParameterValue"
        element="oab_exc:OA_InvalidParameterValue"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="MissingParameterValueFault">
    <wsdl:part name="OA_MissingParameterValue"
        element="oab_exc:OA_MissingParameterValue"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="NoApplicableCodeFault">
    <wsdl:part name="OA_NoApplicableCode" element="oab_exc:OA_NoApplicableCode"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="InternalErrorFault">
    <wsdl:part name="OA_InternalError" element="oab_exc:OA_InternalError"/>
</wsdl:message>
```

```
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="ReferentialIntegrityFault">
  <wsdl:part name="OA_ReferentialIntegrityException"
    element="ums_exc:OA_ReferentialIntegrityException"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="SubjectNotFoundFault">
  <wsdl:part name="OA_SubjectNotFoundException"
    element="ums_exc:OA_SubjectNotFoundException"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="PrincipalNotFoundFault">
  <wsdl:part name="OA_PrincipalNotFoundException"
    element="authen_exc:OA_PrincipalNotFoundException"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="NoSuchMemberFault">
  <wsdl:part name="OA_NoSuchMemberException"
    element="ums_exc:OA_NoSuchMemberException"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="PermissionDeniedFault">
  <wsdl:part name="OA_PermissionDeniedException"
    element="author_exc:OA_PermissionDeniedException"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="VersionNegotiationFailed">
  <wsdl:part name="OA_VersionNegotiationFailed"
    element="oab_exc:OA_VersionNegotiationFailed"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="UnsupportedCapSchema">
  <wsdl:part name="OA_UnsupportedCapSchema"
    element="oab_exc:OA_UnsupportedCapSchema"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:portType name="UserManagementService">
  <wsdl:documentation>
    The User Management Service allows authorised users (e.g. system administrators)
    to add new users and user groups to an OSN and to remove them as well. This
    functionality is required w.r.t. to the way how user access to resources (features, services) is granted in an OSN:
    - Access control is performed by an authorisation and authentication service. The authorisation service can assign access rights to users and user groups.
    - Once being created, users can grant other users access to their resources by means of the authorisation service.
    Example usage:
    A group of users concerned with forest fire manages features such as maps describing fire damage. Another group of users working on flood risk analysis would
    like to access the maps because they are relevant for their planning. Therefore, read
```

```
        access is granted to the flood analysis group for all features created by the
        forest fire
        group.
    </wsdl:documentation>
    <wsdl:operation name="getCapabilities">
        <wsdl:input name="capabilitiesRequest" message="ums:getCapabilitiesRequest"/>
        <wsdl:output name="capabilitiesResponse"
            message="ums:getCapabilitiesResponse"/>
        <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
            message="ums:InvalidParameterValueFault"/>
        <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
            message="ums:MissingParameterValueFault"/>
        <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="ums:NoApplicableCodeFault"/>
        <wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="ums:InternalErrorFault"/>
        <wsdl:fault name="VersionNegotiationFailed"
            message="ums:VersionNegotiationFailed"/>
        <wsdl:fault name="UnsupportedCapSchema"
            message="ums:UnsupportedCapSchema"/>
    </wsdl:operation>
    <wsdl:operation name="removePrincipalFromSubject">
        <wsdl:input name="removePrincipalFromSubjectRequestRequest"
            message="ums:removePrincipalFromSubjectRequest"/>
        <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
            message="ums:InvalidParameterValueFault"/>
        <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
            message="ums:MissingParameterValueFault"/>
        <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="ums:NoApplicableCodeFault"/>
        <wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="ums:InternalErrorFault"/>
        <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied" message="ums:PermissionDeniedFault"/>
        <wsdl:fault name="PrincipalNotFound" message="ums:PrincipalNotFoundFault"/>
        <wsdl:fault name="SubjectNotFound" message="ums:SubjectNotFoundFault"/>
    </wsdl:operation>
    <wsdl:operation name="removePrincipalFromGroup">
        <wsdl:input name="removePrincipalFromGroupRequestRequest"
            message="ums:removePrincipalFromGroupRequest"/>
        <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
            message="ums:InvalidParameterValueFault"/>
        <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
            message="ums:MissingParameterValueFault"/>
        <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="ums:NoApplicableCodeFault"/>
        <wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="ums:InternalErrorFault"/>
        <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied" message="ums:PermissionDeniedFault"/>
        <wsdl:fault name="PrincipalNotFound" message="ums:PrincipalNotFoundFault"/>
        <wsdl:fault name="SubjectNotFound" message="ums:SubjectNotFoundFault"/>
    </wsdl:operation>
```

```
<wsdl:fault name="NoSuchMember" message="ums:NoSuchMemberFault" />
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="addPrincipalToGroup">
  <wsdl:input name="addPrincipalToGroupRequestRequest"
    message="ums:addPrincipalToGroupRequest" />
  <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
    message="ums:InvalidParameterValueFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
    message="ums:MissingParameterValueFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="ums:NoApplicableCodeFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="ums:InternalErrorFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied" message="ums:PermissionDeniedFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="PrincipalNotFound" message="ums:PrincipalNotFoundFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="SubjectNotFound" message="ums:SubjectNotFoundFault" />
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="addPrincipalToSubject">
  <wsdl:input name="addPrincipalToSubjectRequestRequest"
    message="ums:addPrincipalToSubjectRequest" />
  <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
    message="ums:InvalidParameterValueFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
    message="ums:MissingParameterValueFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="ums:NoApplicableCodeFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="ums:InternalErrorFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied" message="ums:PermissionDeniedFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="PrincipalNotFound" message="ums:PrincipalNotFoundFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="SubjectNotFound" message="ums:SubjectNotFoundFault" />
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="getGroups">
  <wsdl:input name="getGroupsRequestRequest"
    message="ums:getGroupsRequest" />
  <wsdl:output name="getGroupsRequestResponse"
    message="ums:getGroupsResponse" />
  <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
    message="ums:InvalidParameterValueFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
    message="ums:MissingParameterValueFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="ums:NoApplicableCodeFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="ums:InternalErrorFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied" message="ums:PermissionDeniedFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="SubjectNotFound" message="ums:SubjectNotFoundFault" />
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="getSubjects">
  <wsdl:input name="getSubjectsRequestRequest"
```

```
        message="ums:getSubjectsRequest" />
<wsdl:output name="getSubjectsRequestResponse"
    message="ums:getSubjectsResponse" />
<wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
    message="ums:InvalidParameterValueFault" />
<wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
    message="ums:MissingParameterValueFault" />
<wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="ums:NoApplicableCodeFault" />
<wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="ums:InternalErrorFault" />
<wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied" message="ums:PermissionDeniedFault" />
<wsdl:fault name="SubjectNotFound" message="ums:SubjectNotFoundFault" />
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="updateGroup">
    <wsdl:documentation>
        Edit attributes of an existing user-group.

        Input:
        User group identification
        User identifications

        Output:
        none
    </wsdl:documentation>
    <wsdl:input name="updateGroupRequestRequest"
        message="ums:updateGroupRequest" />
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
        message="ums:InvalidParameterValueFault" />
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
        message="ums:MissingParameterValueFault" />
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="ums:NoApplicableCodeFault" />
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="ums:InternalErrorFault" />
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied" message="ums:PermissionDeniedFault" />
    <wsdl:fault name="SubjectNotFound" message="ums:SubjectNotFoundFault" />
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="deleteGroup">
    <wsdl:documentation>
        Delete OSN user group.

        Input:
        User group identification

        Output:
        none
    </wsdl:documentation>
```

```
<wsdl:input name="deleteGroupRequestRequest"
            message="ums:deleteGroupRequest"/>
<wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
            message="ums:InvalidParameterValueFault"/>
<wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
            message="ums:MissingParameterValueFault"/>
<wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="ums:NoApplicableCodeFault"/>
<wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="ums:InternalErrorFault"/>
<wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied" message="ums:PermissionDeniedFault"/>
<wsdl:fault name="SubjectNotFound" message="ums:SubjectNotFoundFault"/>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="createGroup">
  <wsdl:documentation>
    Create new OSN user group.

    Input:
    User group identification
    User identifications

    Output:
    none
  </wsdl:documentation>
  <wsdl:input name="createGroupRequestRequest"
              message="ums:createGroupRequest"/>
  <wsdl:output name="createGroupRequestResponse"
              message="ums:createGroupResponse"/>
  <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
              message="ums:InvalidParameterValueFault"/>
  <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
              message="ums:MissingParameterValueFault"/>
  <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="ums:NoApplicableCodeFault"/>
  <wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="ums:InternalErrorFault"/>
  <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied" message="ums:PermissionDeniedFault"/>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="updateSubject">
  <wsdl:documentation>
    Edit attributes of an existing Subject

    Input:
    User identification
    User attributes (e.g. user name, address, email, phone, fax, preferred
    language)

    Output:
```

```
        none
    </wsdl:documentation>
    <wsdl:input name="updateSubjectRequestRequest"
        message="ums:updateSubjectRequest" />
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
        message="ums:InvalidParameterValueFault" />
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
        message="ums:MissingParameterValueFault" />
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="ums:NoApplicableCodeFault" />
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="ums:InternalErrorFault" />
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied" message="ums:PermissionDeniedFault" />
    <wsdl:fault name="SubjectNotFound" message="ums:SubjectNotFoundFault" />
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="deleteSubject">
    <wsdl:documentation>
        Delete OSN Subject.

        Input:
        User identification

        Output:
        none
    </wsdl:documentation>
    <wsdl:input name="deleteSubjectRequestRequest"
        message="ums:deleteSubjectRequest" />
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
        message="ums:InvalidParameterValueFault" />
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
        message="ums:MissingParameterValueFault" />
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="ums:NoApplicableCodeFault" />
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="ums:InternalErrorFault" />
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied" message="ums:PermissionDeniedFault" />
    <wsdl:fault name="ReferentialIntegrity" message="ums:ReferentialIntegrityFault" />
    <wsdl:fault name="SubjectNotFound" message="ums:SubjectNotFoundFault" />
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="createSubject">
    <wsdl:documentation>
        Create new OSN Subject

        Input:
        User identification
        User attributes (e.g. user name, address, email, phone, fax, preferred
        language).
```

```
        Output:
        none
    </wsdl:documentation>
    <wsdl:input name="createSubjectRequestRequest"
        message="ums:createSubjectRequest"/>
    <wsdl:output name="createSubjectRequestResponse"
        message="ums:createSubjectResponse"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
        message="ums:InvalidParameterValueFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
        message="ums:MissingParameterValueFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="ums:NoApplicableCodeFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="ums:InternalErrorFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied" message="ums:PermissionDeniedFault"/>
</wsdl:operation>
</wsdl:portType>
<wsdl:binding name="UserManagementService" type="ums:UserManagementService">
    <wsdl:documentation>
        The User Management Service allows authorised users (e.g. system administra-
tors)
        to add new users and user groups to an OSN and to remove them as well. This
        functionality is required w.r.t. to the way how user access to resources (fea-
tures, ser-
vices) is granted in an OSN:
        - Access control is performed by an authorisation and authentication
        service. The authorisation service can assign access rights to users
        and user groups.
        - Once being created, users can grant other users access to their re-
        sources by means of the authorisation service.
        Example usage:
        A group of users concerned with forest fire manages features such as maps
        describing fire damage. Another group of users working on flood risk analysis
        would like to access the maps because they are relevant for their planning.
        Therefore, read access is granted to the flood analysis group for all features
        created by the forest fire
        group.
    </wsdl:documentation>
    <soap:binding style="document" transport="http://schemas.xmlsoap.org/soap/http"/>
    <wsdl:operation name="getCapabilities">
        <soap:operation soapAction="getCapabilities" style="document"/>
        <wsdl:input>
            <soap:body use="literal"/>
        </wsdl:input>
        <wsdl:output>
            <soap:body use="literal"/>
        </wsdl:output>
    </wsdl:operation>
</wsdl:binding>
</wsdl:service>
</wsdl:definitions>
```

```
<wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
    <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
    <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
    <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="InternalServerError">
    <soap:fault name="InternalServerError" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="UnsupportedCapSchema">
    <soap:fault name="UnsupportedCapSchema" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="VersionNegotiationFailed">
    <soap:fault name="VersionNegotiationFailed" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="removePrincipalFromSubject">
    <soap:operation soapAction="removePrincipalFromSubject" style="document"/>
    <wsdl:input>
        <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:input>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
        <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalServerError">
        <soap:fault name="InternalServerError" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied">
        <soap:fault name="PermissionDenied" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="PrincipalNotFound">
        <soap:fault name="PrincipalNotFound" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="SubjectNotFound">
        <soap:fault name="SubjectNotFound" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
```

```
        </wsdl:fault>
    </wsdl:operation>
    <wsdl:operation name="removePrincipalFromGroup">
        <soap:operation soapAction="removePrincipalFromGroup" style="document"/>
        <wsdl:input>
            <soap:body use="literal"/>
        </wsdl:input>
        <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
            <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal"/>
        </wsdl:fault>
        <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
            <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal"/>
        </wsdl:fault>
        <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
            <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal"/>
        </wsdl:fault>
        <wsdl:fault name="InternalServerError">
            <soap:fault name="InternalServerError" use="literal"/>
        </wsdl:fault>
        <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied">
            <soap:fault name="PermissionDenied" use="literal"/>
        </wsdl:fault>
        <wsdl:fault name="PrincipalNotFound">
            <soap:fault name="PrincipalNotFound" use="literal"/>
        </wsdl:fault>
        <wsdl:fault name="SubjectNotFound">
            <soap:fault name="SubjectNotFound" use="literal"/>
        </wsdl:fault>
        <wsdl:fault name="NoSuchMember">
            <soap:fault name="NoSuchMember" use="literal"/>
        </wsdl:fault>
    </wsdl:operation>
    <wsdl:operation name="addPrincipalToGroup">
        <soap:operation soapAction="addPrincipalToGroup" style="document"/>
        <wsdl:input>
            <soap:body use="literal"/>
        </wsdl:input>
        <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
            <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal"/>
        </wsdl:fault>
        <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
            <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal"/>
        </wsdl:fault>
        <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
```

```
        <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalError">
        <soap:fault name="InternalError" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied">
        <soap:fault name="PermissionDenied" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="PrincipalNotFound">
        <soap:fault name="PrincipalNotFound" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="SubjectNotFound">
        <soap:fault name="SubjectNotFound" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="addPrincipalToSubject">
    <soap:operation soapAction="addPrincipalToSubject" style="document"/>
    <wsdl:input>
        <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:input>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
        <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalError">
        <soap:fault name="InternalError" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied">
        <soap:fault name="PermissionDenied" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="PrincipalNotFound">
        <soap:fault name="PrincipalNotFound" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="SubjectNotFound">
        <soap:fault name="SubjectNotFound" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="getGroups">
    <soap:operation soapAction="getGroups" style="document"/>
```

```
<wsdl:input>
    <soap:body use="literal"/>
</wsdl:input>
<wsdl:output>
    <soap:body use="literal"/>
</wsdl:output>
<wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
    <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
    <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
    <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="InternalError">
    <soap:fault name="InternalError" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied">
    <soap:fault name="PermissionDenied" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="SubjectNotFound">
    <soap:fault name="SubjectNotFound" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="getSubjects">
    <soap:operation soapAction="getSubjects" style="document"/>
    <wsdl:input>
        <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:input>
    <wsdl:output>
        <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:output>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
        <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalError">
        <soap:fault name="InternalError" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
```

```
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied">
    <soap:fault name="PermissionDenied" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="SubjectNotFound">
    <soap:fault name="SubjectNotFound" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="updateGroup">
    <wsdl:documentation>
        Edit attributes of an existing user-group.

        Input:
        User group identification
        User identifications

        Output:
        none
    </wsdl:documentation>
    <soap:operation soapAction="updateGroup" style="document"/>
    <wsdl:input>
        <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:input>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
        <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalServerError">
        <soap:fault name="InternalServerError" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied">
        <soap:fault name="PermissionDenied" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="SubjectNotFound">
        <soap:fault name="SubjectNotFound" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="deleteGroup">
    <wsdl:documentation>
```

```
        Delete OSN user group.

        Input:
        User group identification

        Output:
        none
    </wsdl:documentation>
    <soap:operation soapAction="deleteGroup" style="document" />
    <wsdl:input>
        <soap:body use="literal" />
    </wsdl:input>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal" />
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal" />
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
        <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal" />
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalServerError">
        <soap:fault name="InternalServerError" use="literal" />
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied">
        <soap:fault name="PermissionDenied" use="literal" />
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="SubjectNotFound">
        <soap:fault name="SubjectNotFound" use="literal" />
    </wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="createGroup">
    <wsdl:documentation>
        Create new OSN user group.

        Input:
        User group identification
        User identifications

        Output:
        none
    </wsdl:documentation>
    <soap:operation soapAction="createGroup" style="document" />
    <wsdl:input>
```

```
        <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:input>
    <wsdl:output>
        <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:output>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
        <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalError">
        <soap:fault name="InternalError" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied">
        <soap:fault name="PermissionDenied" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="updateSubject">
    <wsdl:documentation>
        Edit attributes of an existing Subject

        Input:
        User identification
        User attributes (e.g. user name, address, email, phone, fax, preferred
        language)

        Output:
        none
    </wsdl:documentation>
    <soap:operation soapAction="updateSubject" style="document"/>
    <wsdl:input>
        <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:input>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
```

```
        <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalError">
        <soap:fault name="InternalError" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied">
        <soap:fault name="PermissionDenied" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="SubjectNotFound">
        <soap:fault name="SubjectNotFound" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="deleteSubject">
    <wsdl:documentation>
        Delete OSN Subject.

        Input:
        User identification

        Output:
        none
    </wsdl:documentation>
    <soap:operation soapAction="deleteSubject" style="document"/>
    <wsdl:input>
        <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:input>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
        <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalError">
        <soap:fault name="InternalError" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied">
        <soap:fault name="PermissionDenied" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="ReferentialIntegrity">
        <soap:fault name="ReferentialIntegrity" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
```

```
<wsdl:fault name="SubjectNotFound">
    <soap:fault name="SubjectNotFound" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="createSubject">
    <wsdl:documentation>
        Create new OSN Subject

        Input:
        User identification
        User attributes (e.g. user name, address, email, phone, fax, preferred
        language).

        Output:
        none
    </wsdl:documentation>
    <soap:operation soapAction="createSubject" style="document"/>
    <wsdl:input>
        <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:input>
    <wsdl:output>
        <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:output>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
        <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalServerError">
        <soap:fault name="InternalServerError" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied">
        <soap:fault name="PermissionDenied" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
</wsdl:binding>
<wsdl:service name="UserManagementService">
    <wsdl:port name="UserManagementService" binding="ums:UserManagementService">
        <soap:address
            location="http://stl-d-pl1.htw-
```

```
        saarland.de:8080/axis2/services/UserManagementService"/>  
    </wsdl:port>  
</wsdl:service>  
</wsdl:definitions>
```

6 Appendix B: UML Model

6.1 Static model

6.2 Dynamic model

Create a new subject

Add a principal to a subject

